
MACHINE LEARNING WITH DATA AUGMENTATION FOR CONCRETE CONSTITUTIVE MODELLING

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Abstract: Reinforced concrete structures are still a very common composite material in Civil Engineering due to their low cost and high performance in buildings and structures. The behavior of such material is highly nonlinear even in the early stages of loading. Failure modes such as cracking, crushing, splitting, etc. can lead the material to ultimate strength. Plasticity and viscoelasticity are also responsible for the nonlinear behavior. A set of experimental data, reported as a database by Kupfer et al. (1969), is used for such behavior in plane stress, for various stress ratios and concrete strengths. So, like the paper of Ghabhoussi et al (1991), a Machine Learning (ML) approach to model the nonlinear behavior (stress-strain curves) of concrete is proposed in this paper. Techniques of data augmentation are used to expand the original database and different ML models. The results show that ML can predict and represent very well the nonlinear behavior by comparing the experimental stress-strain curves with those obtained by ML. Furthermore, the ML was able to predict the Failure Surface (for any failure mode) for the concrete.

1 Introduction

Artificial neural networks (ANNs), commonly referred to as neural networks, are computational models that are modeled after the architecture and operation of biological neural networks found in the human brain. They are made up of layers of networked nodes, also referred to as neurons or units. Every neuron in the network takes incoming signals, processes them using an activation function, and then outputs a signal that could be transmitted to other neurons (Ghabhoussi et al., 1999). The field of material modeling has seen a revolution recently due to breakthroughs in neural networks, particularly in creative learning algorithms. Constitutive modeling in information science is learning about a material and expressing it with an emphasis on its intricate behavior. Neural networks' capacity for self-organization and learning can be used to create behavioral models of materials if there is enough information on the materials' responses to outside stimuli.

This paper improves, with the data augmentation technique, an ANN model (Ghabhoussi et al, 1991) to predict stress-strain curves for concrete in a biaxial stress state, based on experimental data from (Kupfer et al, 1969).

2 Theoretical Basis

Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) are computer algorithms based on the concept of machine learning. The basic structure behind ANNs is similar to that of a biological neuron, i.e.: body, transmission lines, axon, and dendrite. Feedforward neural networks are a fundamental type of artificial neural network where connections between nodes do not form cycles. Information flows in one direction, from input nodes through

hidden layers (if present) to output nodes. These networks are commonly used for supervised learning tasks such as classification and regression. The network architecture consists of an input layer, one or more hidden layers, and an output layer. Each layer contains interconnected nodes (neurons), and connections between nodes are associated with weights that are learned during training. Feedforward neural networks utilize activation functions to introduce nonlinearity into the network, enabling them to learn complex patterns and relationships in the data. Training typically involves adjusting the weights of connections using optimization algorithms such as backpropagation to minimize the difference between predicted and actual outputs (Haykin, 1998). Feedforward neural networks have been successfully applied in various domains, including image recognition and natural language processing, and are used in this paper. In the training phase, the output signal is sent back to the input in an interactive process to reduce the error. Truncation takes place using criteria such as the number of interactions or the final admissible error. Figure 1 illustrates the operation of an artificial neural network, ANN, with several 4 input neurons, 2 hidden layers with 5 and 3 neurons, and an output layer with 2 neurons (with architecture [4 5 3 2]). Each neuron unit operates as $y = f(\mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{X} + b)$, where \mathbf{W}^T is the vector of weights b the threshold for trigger (to be determined), \mathbf{X} the vector of input signals, and f a nonlinear activation function. The training is performed by minimization (using a learning rate η) of an Error function (generally the MSE, Mean Squared Error) and using the backpropagation algorithm.

Fig. 1 (a)ANN representation with a [4 5 3 2] architecture. (b) Neuron activity function representation.

3 Methodology

All the data was digitized from the Kupfer et al (1969) curves till failure composed by $\sigma_1/f_c \times \varepsilon_1$, $\sigma_1/f_c \times \varepsilon_2$, $\sigma_2/f_c \times \varepsilon_1$ and $\sigma_2/f_c \times \varepsilon_2$ where σ_1 and σ_2 are the principal stresses, ε_1 and ε_2 are the principal strains and f_c is the compressive ultimate strength of concrete, all obtained in a series of experimental tests. The architecture used by Ghabhoussi et al, 1991 is depicted in Figure 2. Thus, the input parameters are the principal stresses, the principal strains of a certain point the stress-strain curve, and the incremental principal stresses to obtain the next point in the graph. The output was the incremental principal strains, $\Delta \epsilon^{k+1} = \mathcal{N}_1(\sigma^k, \epsilon^k, \Delta \sigma^k)$, where σ and ϵ are the principal stress and strain, respectively, k is an incremental step and \mathcal{N} represents the ANN. For a Finite Element Method implementation, the incremental stresses become de output, and the incremental strains, the inputs, $\Delta \sigma^{k+1} = \mathcal{N}_2(\sigma^k, \epsilon^k, \Delta \epsilon^k)$.

Fig. 2 (a) Architecture used by Ghabhoussi et al, 1991 for the biaxial stress-strain curve constitutive modeling. (b) Experimental stress paths (Kupfer et al., 1991) that compose the dataset for training and validation curves.

Values for the principal stress ratio to define the stress-strain paths used for training and validating (Fig. 2b) are: $\sigma_1/\sigma_2 = \{-1/-1; -1/-0.52; -1/0.0; -1/-0.2; -1/-0.5; -1/-0.7; -1/0.204; -1/0.103; -1/0.052; -1/0.02; -1/0.04; -1/0.10; 1/1; 0.55/1; 0/1; 0.25/1; 0.5/1\}$ and also $\{\sigma_2 = 0.343\sigma_1 - 0.571\sigma_1^2 \text{ and } \sigma_2 = -0.221\sigma_1 - 0.214\sigma_1^2\}$. In the end, there were 26 graphs, each with two principal stress versus principal strain, totaling 52 stress \times strain experimental graphs.

3.1 Data Augmentation

For the data augmentation, it was chosen to interpolate the points from the digitized/discretized curves using spline curves that, in the end, fitted very well with all the experimental data. Afterward, the fitted spline curves were resampled with a higher number of points, 10 times more data than the original experimental data. Typical digitized experimental data (symbols) and the augmented data (dashed line) are presented in Fig.3.

Fig. 3 Typical digitized original experimental data (symbols) and the augmented data by spline interpolation (dashed lines).

4 Numerical results

The best architecture for the ANN used was [12 15 4]. All the dataset was randomly separated in training, validating and testing sets with a proportion of 70%, 15%, and 15%. The Levenberg Marquardt backpropagation algorithm was used for the task. Figure 4 shows the MSE error and a comparison of the 2 outputs $\Delta\epsilon_1, \Delta\epsilon_{12}$ for the testing set (unseen data by the ANN), showing the ANN was correctly trained, presenting a good generalization without overfitting.

Fig. 4 Typical MSE error for the two outputs $\Delta\epsilon_1$ and $\Delta\epsilon_2$ for the trained ANN in the validation set.

Figure 5 shows some comparative curves corresponding to the validation data set for the stress-strain curves with a good correlation with the experimental data from Kupfer et al. (1969). Figure 6 shows that using the same ANN, one can notice that the failure prediction is quite good (cyan continuous line) when compared to the previous original experimental data (black dots) for the surface failure of plain concrete.

Fig. 5 Typical results after training for $\sigma/f_c \times \epsilon$ curves compared to the experimental data (dashed line are the ANN prediction).

Fig. 6 Results after training for $\sigma_1 \times \sigma_2$ curve compared to the experimental data(dots) and ANN prediction (cyan continuous line).

Combined with this surface, the algorithm can also determine how far away a particular point is from failure based on where it is within the surface, whether it's far away or not. Figure 7 shows the module of a distance vector based on the nearest point (perpendicular) to the surface for both (a) Experimental Data and (b) ANN. One can notice that the values are slightly different, presenting a difference of up to 2%.

5 Final Remarks and Conclusions

The presented paper implemented feedforward-backpropagation ANNs to predict stress-strain curves for the composite material concrete. The dataset was based on experiments from Kupfer et al. (1969) and the data augmentation technique was used to improve the training. The MSE error was very low in the validation dataset, meaning a good generalization for the trained ANN architecture and confirmed by the superposition of the predicted-measured stress-strain curves in several scenarios of the plane stress. The proposed methodology is ready for practical implementation in a Finite Element software as a material nonlinearity module in future studies.

Fig. 7 Results after training for $\sigma_1 \times \sigma_2$ curve compared to the (a) Experimental data (blue dots) and (b) the trained ANN prediction (cyan dots).

5.1 Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

5.2 CRediT author statement

Paola M. Albino: Methodology, Software, Writing-original draft. **H. M. Gomes:** Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Supervision, Writing-review.

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